

1 Research Article

2 **Anaerobic co-digestion of waste yeast biomass from citric acid production and waste frying fat**

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15 **Keywords:** anaerobic digestion, citric acid, waste frying fat, *Yarrowia lipolytica*, yeast

16

17 **Abbreviations:** **COD**, chemical oxygen demand; **CSTR**, continuous stirred tank reactor; **CYB**,

18 concentrated yeast biomass; **LCFA**, long-chain fatty acids; **LR**, loading rate; **OLR**, organic loading

19 rate; **SBY**, specific biogas yield; **SMY**, specific methane yield; **TN**, total nitrogen; **TOC**, total organic

20 carbon; **TS**, total solids; **VFA**, volatile fatty acids (sum of concentrations of acetate, propionate and

21 butyrate); **VS**, volatile solids; **WFF**, waste frying fat

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31 **Practical application**

32 Recent trends in biotechnology favor a holistic approach to microbial processes, aiming at
33 implementing a bio-based ‘circular flow’ economy that achieves multiple, resource-efficient uses of
34 raw materials and material streams. By-products formerly regarded as waste are now regarded as
35 secondary resources. Accordingly, anaerobic digestion is a structural component in the value chain.
36 For example, waste yeast biomass from citric acid production can be re-used as a substrate for biogas
37 production. This research work deals with the challenges and limitations of the anaerobic digestion of
38 waste yeast biomass as a mono-substrate and co-substrate. It provides new insights into designing a
39 novel bio-refinery system that uses organic residues from waste-based production processes to
40 maximize the value derived from the residual biomass. These findings will be of particular interest to
41 those engaged in the development of anaerobic digestion and waste-based production processes, and in
42 bio-based sectors in general.

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59 **Abstract**

60 The application of spent yeast for biogas production has been studied only in the context of breweries
61 so far. This study is focused on the anaerobic digestion of concentrated yeast biomass (CYB), being a
62 by-product of citric acid biosynthesis. Two experimental set-ups were used in order to test CYB as a
63 mono-substrate and co-substrate for closing the loop in accordance with the 'bioeconomy' approach.
64 The results show that CYB allows for obtaining a high biogas yield, with a maximum of $1.45 \text{ m}^3_{\text{N}}/\text{kg}_{\text{VS}}$
65 produced when CYB was used as a mono-substrate. The average methane concentration was $66 \pm 4\%$.
66 However, anaerobic digestion of CYB alone was difficult to perform because of a tendency for over-
67 acidification, meaning that the maximum possible organic loading rate was $1 \text{ kg}/(\text{m}^3 \cdot \text{d})$. Repeated
68 clogging of tubes with coagulated biomass also disturbed continuous feeding.
69 In contrast, the co-digestion of CYB with waste frying fat at a ratio of 1:20 showed stable operation
70 during a 70-day fermentation period. The biogas yield using the substrate mixture was $1.42 \text{ m}^3/\text{kg}_{\text{VS}}$ at
71 an organic loading rate of $2 \text{ kg}/(\text{m}^3 \cdot \text{d})$. The methane concentration reached $67 \pm 4\%$ and the acetate
72 concentration did not exceed 30 mg/L during the entire fermentation.

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87 **1 Introduction**

88 Citric acid is a bulk chemical that is generally produced in biotechnological processes using the fungus
89 *Aspergillus niger* [1]. This production procedure is environmentally problematic because of the
90 heavily polluted solid and liquid wastes that are by-products of citric acid production [2]. An
91 alternative process that uses the “non-conventional” yeast *Yarrowia lipolytica* is more environmentally
92 friendly. *Y. lipolytica* is a non-pathogenic ascomycetous yeast that is able to utilize a series of
93 substrates such as hexoses, *n*-paraffins, fatty acids, fats and oils, organic acids and alcohols as sole
94 carbon sources and can produce valuable products such as single-cell protein, lipases or organic acids
95 (e.g. 2-ketoglutaric acid, citric acid, isocitric acid, and pyruvic acid) depending on the cultivation
96 conditions [3, 4]. Our previous research concerned the optimization of citric acid production with *Y.*
97 *lipolytica* H181 using glucose and sucrose (e.g. [5, 6]) and plant oils [7] as carbon sources. Other
98 authors have reported on the utilization of various waste materials such as industrial fat [8], raw
99 glycerol and crustacean waste [9], industrial raw molasses [10] and olive mill wastewater [11] for the
100 production of citric acid, single cell oils, polyols and lipids with *Y. lipolytica*.

101 Current research into biotechnological processes is increasingly aiming at achieving holistic use of all
102 process inputs and outputs, i.e. substrates and by-products. Taking the perspective of the
103 ‘bioeconomy’ approach, new activities are focusing on the design of bio-refineries where production
104 residues are considered as a secondary resource for subsequent production; the last step of residue
105 conversion is biogas production for energy purposes [12]. Biogas is a mixture of mainly methane and
106 carbon dioxide that is produced by anaerobic digestion degradation (also commonly referred to as
107 anaerobic digestion) of biogenic materials – renewables or organic wastes. In the course of
108 downstream processing after citric acid production, concentrated yeast biomass (CYB) is produced as
109 a residue. There has been no research on *Y. lipolytica* digestion so far and only a few publications exist
110 concerning anaerobic digestion from spent yeast from breweries [13-16]. Biogas yield of 0.45-0.72
111 m³/kg_{VS} for brewery surplus yeast [13; 14] and average methane yield of 0.330–0.370 m³_{CH₄}/g_{COD} [15]
112 were reported for batch fermentation tests. When an anaerobic sequencing batch reactor was used, a
113 specific biogas productivity of more than 0.43 m³/kg_{COD} was reached [16]. Moreover, it has been
114 reported that the use of baker’s yeast causes process upsets in full-scale anaerobic digesters such as the

115 formation of foam [17]. Foam formation can cause various problems in biogas plants such as blocking
116 of gas pipes and disruption of measurement devices and recirculating pumps [18, 19, 20]. One possible
117 method of preventing process imbalances is co-digestion with stabilizing substrates. The use of co-
118 substrates with anti-foaming properties is appropriate for substrates that have a high foaming
119 propensity. Kougiyas et al. [21] described the good anti-foaming properties of plant oils, especially
120 rapeseed oil, during anaerobic digestion in overloaded manure-based biogas reactors. The use of WFF
121 that is actually spent rapeseed oil that has been used for frying in a canteen kitchen would thus appear
122 to be advantageous as a co-substrate for CYB.

123 Accordingly, the aim of this research work was to study the mono-digestion of CYB and co-digestion
124 with WFF in semi-continuous fermentation in order to evaluate digestibility and process stability.

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126 **2 Materials and methods**

127 2.1 Digestates and substrates

128 The substrates for the fermentation batch tests and the semi-continuous fermentation experiments were
129 WFF (total solids (TS): 100% wet weight (WW), volatile solids (VS): 100% TS) from a canteen
130 kitchen and a cross-flow filtrated thickened fermentation broth from the cultivation of a non-
131 conventional *Yarrowia lipolytica* H181 yeast (abbr. CYB) (TS: 41.5% WW, VS: 91.4% TS, c
132 (protein) = 0.18 g/L, c (fat) = 0.71 g/g_{TS}, TOC/TN = 70.1). The substrates CYB and WFF were used
133 either in pure form or mixed at a ratio of 1:1 (w/w) or 1:20 (w/w). The inoculum (TS: 7.11% WW,
134 VS: 91.2% TS) for the fermentation batch tests originated from the research biogas plant of the
135 German Biomass Research Centre (DBFZ) (anaerobic digester utilizing maize silage). In the
136 preliminary semi-continuous fermentation experiment, the digestate originated from the secondary
137 digester of a biogas plant that is operated by an agricultural cooperative close to Leipzig, Germany.
138 This digestate had a pH of 8.02, a TS content of 3.93% WW and a VS content of 66.9% TS. The
139 digestate used in the main semi-continuous fermentations originated from the anaerobic digester of the
140 Rosental waste water treatment plant in Leipzig and had a pH of 7.73, TS content of 2.44% WW and
141 VS content of 62.4% TS.

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143 2.2 Technical equipment

144 2.2.1 Batch fermentation test equipment

145 The batch fermentation test equipment consisted of twelve test jars. Each test jar was comprised of a
146 500-mL Schott bottle, a gas trap and a 2-L gas collection tube. Gas-tight pipes were used to transport
147 the biogas produced to the collection pipe. A three-way stopcock was placed between the Schott bottle
148 and the gas trap for taking gas samples in order to analyze the methane content in the produced biogas.
149 The reaction mixtures in the Schott bottles were incubated in a water bath (GFL 1004, Gesellschaft für
150 Labortechnik GmbH, Germany). The collection tubes contained 300 g L⁻¹ sodium chloride and 50 g L⁻¹
151 citric acid solutions as a sealing liquid. A syringe was used for pressure equalization at ambient
152 pressure.

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154 2.2.2 Continuous stirred tank reactor (CSTR)

155 CSTRs with a total volume of 40 L and working volume of 31 L were used for the continuous
156 fermentation experiments. The process temperature was adjusted using a water-heated reactor jacket.
157 A thermostat (Integral T 1200, Lauda, Germany) was used for continuous heating. The bioreactors
158 were fitted with an insulating layer. A combination sensor (FU20, Yokogawa Deutschland GmbH,
159 Germany) determined the pH and temperature levels in the digestate. Biogas production was measured
160 by a drum gas meter (TG05-PVC, Dr.-Ing. RITTER Apparatebau GmbH & Co. KG, Germany).
161 Online measured data, such as biogas production, temperature and pH, was recorded by a data logger.
162 The motor of the stirrer (stirrer RZR 2101 control, Heidolph, Germany) was positioned above the
163 reactor and the stirrer had a rotation speed of 35 rpm. A U-shaped tube filled with distilled water was
164 used as an overpressure and underpressure safety device.
165 The automated feeding system consisted of a hose pump (REGLO Digital, ismaTec, Wertheim,
166 Germany) and a time switch (93256 NK ZSU 4, Goobay, Braunschweig, Germany), which controlled
167 the pump and Schott bottles with the substrates (CYB/water and/or WFF) that were continuously
168 mixed by a magnetic stirrer. The substrate was supplied to the system over various time periods
169 depending on the organic loading rate (OLR) – see experimental set-up for more information.

170 A sample of biogas was taken manually from the reactor once a week using a separate sampling
171 device at the gas measuring section in order to determine the methane content in the biogas.

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173 2.3 Experimental set-up

174 2.3.1 Determination of the specific biogas yield (SBY) using WFF and CYB as well as their mixtures
175 in fermentation batch tests

176 Fermentation tests for the evaluation of the biogas yield were carried out in accordance with the VDI
177 4630 guideline [22]. The inoculum of the test system was sieved through a 5-mm sieve and incubated
178 for 7 days at 37.5 °C prior to the start of the experiment.

179 Four different variants were tested: 1) CYB (VS substrate to VS inoculum ratio = 0.45), 2) WFF (VS
180 substrate to VS inoculum ratio = 0.11), 3) CYB+WFF at a ratio of 1:1 (w/w) (VS substrate to VS
181 inoculum ratio = 0.21), 4) CYB+ WFF at a ratio of 1:20 (w/w) (VS substrate to VS inoculum ratio =
182 0.45). Each variant was performed in duplicate. In addition, two bottles with inoculum served as zero
183 samples. The reaction mixtures were incubated at 38 °C. The fermentation batch tests were performed
184 until the termination criterion (i.e., daily biogas volume equivalent to less than 1% of the total volume
185 of biogas produced up to that time) was met. The methane concentration in biogas was measured twice
186 a week.

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188 2.3.2 Anaerobic digestion of CYB and WFF in continuous fermentation experiments

189 2.3.2.1 Preliminary experiment

190 The mixed substrates of CYB and WFF at a ratio of 1:20 (w/w) were used in the preliminary anaerobic
191 digestion experiment. The substrate supply to the fermenters was initially carried out once a day for 50
192 days. After 51 days, the automatic feeding system was installed and a cycle of 1.5 hours was selected
193 for the timer for continuous addition of the substrate. The experiment was started at an organic loading
194 rate (OLR) of 0.5 kg_{VS}/(m³*d). After an adjustment period of 19 days, the OLR was increased to 1
195 kg_{VS}/(m³*d) and, after 29 days, to 2 kg_{VS}/(m³*d). In order to support the anaerobic digestion process, a
196 nitrogen source, 66.4 g of urea, was added on day 57. After eleven more days, the OLR was increased

197 to 3 kg_{VS}/(m³*d). The hydraulic retention time was 60 days, and was adjusted by adding tap water to
198 the feeding substrate. The preliminary experiment lasted 72 days.

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200 2.3.2.2 Main continuous parallel experiments by use of CYB and CYB-WFF (1:20)

201 Substrate supply was carried out automatically from the very beginning in the main continuous
202 experiments. Two CSTRs were run in parallel. The first CSTR was fed with the CYB-WFF substrate
203 mixture at a ratio of 1:20 (w/w) just as in the case of the preliminary experiment. One Schott bottle
204 was filled with CYB, tap water and later also with urea. Another substrate storage bottle contained
205 only WFF. Sixteen times a day, the automatic feeding system pumped a defined volume of substrate
206 adapted for the specific OLR into the reactor. After an adjustment period of 16 days at an organic
207 loading rate (OLR) of 0.5 kg_{VS}/(m³*d), the OLR was increased to 1 kg_{VS}/(m³*d) and, after 45 days, to
208 1.5 kg_{VS}/(m³*d). In order to support the anaerobic digestion process, a nitrogen source, 0.5 g of urea
209 (corresponding to a loading rate (LR) of 7.5 mg urea-N/(L*d)), was added from day 32 to 35. The urea
210 addition was increased to 1.0 g of urea per day (LR=15.1 mg urea-N/(L*d)) in the period from day 36
211 to 43 and to 1.5 g urea per day (LR=22.6 mg urea-N/(L*d)) from day 44 to 49. From day 50, the
212 daily urea addition was 2.0 g (LR=30.1 mg/(L*d)) and this was not increased any further until the
213 experiment finished after 84 days. The hydraulic retention time was 100 days.

214 In the second CSTR, CYB (100%) was used as a substrate. One Schott bottle was filled with CYB, tap
215 water and later also with urea. After an adjustment period of sixteen days at an OLR of 0.5
216 kg_{VS}/(m³*d), the OLR was increased to 1 kg_{VS}/(m³*d). The HRL was 100 days, adjusted by adding tap
217 water to the feeding substrate bottle for CYB. The addition of urea had to be started on day 32 with 0.5
218 g of urea per day (LR=7.5 mg urea-N/(L*d)). After four more days, urea addition was increased to 1.0
219 g of urea per day (LR=15.1 mg urea-N/(L*d)) and, on day 44, to 1.5 g of urea per day (LR=22.6 mg
220 urea-N/(L*d)). To adapt to the ammonium concentration, urea addition was reduced between days 64
221 and 72 from 1.5 g to 1.0 g of urea per day (i.e. decrease from 22.6 to 15.1 mg urea-N/(L*d)). On day
222 73, urea addition was increased to 1.5 g of urea per day (LR=22.6 mg urea-N/(L*d)) again until the
223 end of the experiment. The experiment lasted 84 days.

224 Samples of digestates of all anaerobic digestion experiments were taken twice a week and analyzed as
225 described below. The process temperature was maintained at 38 °C.

226

227 2.4 Analyses

228 The samples of CYB and digestates from the anaerobic digestion experiments described in 2.3.2 were
229 analyzed directly after sampling.

230 2.4.1 Sample pre-treatment

231 COD, TS and VS were measured in the original samples without pre-treatment. The CYB sample was
232 centrifuged for 5 minutes at 13.000 rpm (Eppendorf centrifuge 5415D,
233 Hamburg, Germany) for the analysis of citric acid concentration. The protein concentration was
234 measured in a filtrate (folded filter, pore size: 2 µm, No. 390, Filtrak, Germany). The fat amount was
235 determined in the freeze-dried sample (Beta2-16, Christ, Germany) and milled by use of a pebble mill
236 (MM301, Retsch, Germany).

237 The digestate samples were passed through a sieve with a mesh size of 0.75 mm. The sieved sample
238 was centrifuged for 10 minutes at 5,300 rpm (Heraeus-Labofuge 200, Thermo Fisher Scientific
239 GmbH, Dreieich, Germany) and filtered afterwards (pressure filtration device SM 16 249, Sartorius,
240 Göttingen, Germany; nylon membrane filter: pore size 0.45 µm, Whatman, Germany) as well as
241 analyzed for ammonium-nitrogen and volatile fatty acids (VFA).

242 2.4.2.2 Sample analyses

243 Once a week, a 20 mL sample of biogas was taken and the biogas composition (methane, hydrogen,
244 nitrogen, and oxygen percentages) was determined by gas chromatography using an Agilent GC 6850
245 WLD wavelength detector (Agilent Technologies, USA) with an HP Plot separation column and argon
246 as the carrier gas. A gas mixture of 49.8% methane and 50.2% nitrogen was used as a calibration gas.

247

248 **3 Results**

249 3.1 Fermentation batch tests

250 The aim of the fermentation batch tests was to explore the digestibility of the two substrates CYB and
251 WFF and of their mixtures. The results that are described in Figure 1 and Table 2 were subsequently
252 used for designing continuous fermentations on a technical laboratory scale.
253 Biogas production started with a delay in the case of WFF as compared to CYB (Figure 1). After two
254 days, $0.02 \pm 0.01 \text{ m}^3_{\text{N}}/\text{kg}_{\text{VS}}$ was produced using WFF, whereas $0.05 \pm 0.01 \text{ m}^3_{\text{N}}/\text{kg}_{\text{VS}}$ was detected for
255 CYB as substrate. Nevertheless, the produced biogas volume of $0.23 \text{ m}^3_{\text{N}}/\text{kg}_{\text{VS}}$ was equal on the fifth
256 day of fermentation, and the batch tests with WFF achieved a significantly higher SBY at the end of
257 the fermentation than those with CYB as a substrate (Table 2). The methane end concentration reached
258 the same value in both test variants.

259 In the case of substrate mixtures, both curves for biogas formation showed a typical diauxic trend due
260 to the delayed digestion start of WFF (Figure 1). After the utilization of CYB with better bio-
261 availability, a lag phase was observed before the WFF was utilized. It can be seen that this lag phase
262 was longer in the case of higher percentages of WFF in the substrate mixture, with the result that the
263 fermentation duration of 48 days was 25% longer than the other batch tests. Nevertheless, the results
264 showed that the mixture of CYB and WFF at a ratio of 1:20 is more favorable than the 1:1 mixture of
265 these two substrate components because in this case both the SBY and the SMY were higher.

266

267 3.2 Continuous fermentation of a substrate mixture of CYB and WFF

268 The aim of the experiment was to test the substrate combination of CYB and WFF at a ratio of 1:20
269 (w/w) based on VS in a continuous fermentation.

270 The limits of the usage of the given substrate mixture were tested in a preliminary experiment. The
271 SBY and the profiles of the VFA concentrations are displayed in Figure 2A. During the first six days
272 after the start of the fermentation, the SBY showed a large peak of $1.61 \text{ m}^3_{\text{N}}/\text{kg}_{\text{VS}}$ on day 4, dropping
273 again to $0.75 \text{ m}^3_{\text{N}}/\text{kg}_{\text{VS}}$ on day 6. Further SBY decreased slightly until the increase of OLR to 1
274 $\text{kg}/(\text{m}^3 \cdot \text{d})$. Thereafter, the SBY showed a linear increase ($R^2 = 0.998$) until day 37. The substrate
275 feeding period of once a day caused no problems during the first 38 days. However, after the increase
276 of the OLR to $2 \text{ kg}/(\text{m}^3 \cdot \text{d})$ the SBY showed peaks with a very high amplitude of about $2 \text{ L}_{\text{N}}/\text{h}$ between
277 the daily maximum and minimum values (Figure 2B). In order to avoid strong fluctuations in biogas

278 production, automatically controlled pumping of both substrates was put into operation. The result
279 shows an improvement of the biogas production curve. After increasing the OLR to 3 kg/(m³*d), the
280 pH dropped from 7.9 to 7.2 (data not shown). Substrate feeding was discontinued in order to achieve
281 stabilization of the process. Thus, the SBY, which represents biogas production relative to the volatile
282 solids added in substrates, was zero during this time (Figure 2A). SBY dropped very quickly and
283 reached zero within four days. Despite the interrupted feeding, over-acidification proceeded with the
284 result that the digestate contained 5.2 g/L of acetate at the end of the experiment.

285 The methane concentration was lower than 60% during the phase with an OLR of 0.5 kg/(m³*d) and
286 stabilized during OLRs of 1 and 2 kg/(m³*d) at a methane content in biogas of 67.2 ± 2%. After the
287 switch to an OLR of 3 kg/(m³*d), the methane content decreased to 52.3% by the last feeding day (day
288 66).

289 The experience obtained in the preliminary experiment was applied to continuous fermentation using
290 digestate from a WWTP as an inoculum and the CYB-WFF (1:20) substrate mixture. In this
291 experiment, the continuous feeding strategy was used from the very beginning, the hydraulic retention
292 time was extended from 60 to 100 days and the maximum OLR was set to 2 kg/(m³*d) using smaller
293 steps of 0.5 kg/(m³*d).

294 Biogas production showed some fluctuations during the first two OLR periods (Figure 3A). As in the
295 preliminary experiment, the SBY reached its maximum of 1.63 m³_N/kg_{Vs} on day 4, with a strongly
296 declining tendency thereafter. There are drops in biogas production on the days when the OLR was
297 changed due to the manipulation of the feeding pumps during their re-calibration. The drop in SBY on
298 days 35 and 36 was due to a defective drum gas meter. In general, the biogas production curve
299 flattened with advancing fermentation time. Any noticeable fluctuations occurred during an OLR of 2
300 kg/(m³*d) and the SBY reached 1.32 ± 0.02 m³_N/g_{Vs} during this period. The methane concentration
301 was stable at 67.0 ± 4.1% during the whole fermentation time. As regards VFAs, only acetate was
302 detected in the digestate throughout the entire fermentation time and the acetate concentration did not
303 exceed 30 mg/L (Figure 3A).

304 The nitrogen addition, pH value, TOC/TN ratio, and ammonium-nitrogen concentration in the course
305 of the experiment are shown in Figure 3B. The pH value of 6.85 ± 0.12 was almost stable during the

306 fermentation showing some small fluctuations. The TOC/TN ratio increased from an initial value of
307 2.92 to 4.06 on the day when nitrogen supplementation started (day 32) and stagnated at a value of
308 3.74 ± 0.12 thereafter.

309 The ammonium-nitrogen concentration dropped from almost 1 g/L to 0.6 g/L during the first 32 days.
310 Thereafter, urea was added to the substrate mixture in order to prevent nitrogen limitation. As a result
311 of this measure, the ammonium-nitrogen concentration stabilized and was 0.8 g/L at the end of the
312 fermentation.

313 The TS content was stable at a value of $2.37 \pm 0.15\%$ of fresh mass during the whole experiment. The
314 VS content was $65.6 \pm 6.59\%$ TS during the fermentation, with a slightly increasing tendency after the
315 change to an OLR of $1.5 \text{ kg}/(\text{m}^3 \cdot \text{d})$.

316 There was one foaming event during the fermentation in the night between days 15 and 16, when the
317 digestate foamed to the top of the digester. No countermeasures were necessary because of the rapid
318 fall of the foam.

319

320 3.3 Continuous fermentation using CYB

321 The aim of this experiment was to test the possibility of using the substrate CYB in continuous
322 fermentation with automated feeding. The SBY curve is shown in Figure 4A. During the first period
323 with an OLR of $0.5 \text{ kg}/(\text{m}^3 \cdot \text{d})$, the biogas yield fluctuated initially and stabilized subsequently at
324 values of about $0.70 \text{ m}^3_{\text{N}}/\text{kg}_{\text{VS}}$. After the increase of the OLR to $1 \text{ kg}/(\text{m}^3 \cdot \text{d})$, the SBY initially
325 dropped to $0.42 \text{ m}^3_{\text{N}}/\text{kg}_{\text{VS}}$ due to the recalibration of the substrate pump. The SBY stabilized at a value
326 of $0.73 \pm 0.04 \text{ m}^3_{\text{N}}/\text{kg}_{\text{VS}}$ thereafter until the time of starting the addition of urea for nitrogen
327 supplementation on day 32. Nitrogen addition was necessary due to the high C/N ratio of the substrate
328 used (TOC/TN = 70.1). The mono-digestion of the CYB resulted in a shift in the TOC/TN ratio in the
329 digestate from an initial value of 2.9 to 4.3 on day 32 (Figure 4B). After the urea addition, the
330 TOC/TN ratio stayed almost constant and the biogas yield increased rapidly to values of up to 1.45
331 $\text{m}^3_{\text{N}}/\text{kg}_{\text{VS}}$ as a maximum (days 69 and 77). The VFA concentrations reached their maximum of almost
332 4,139 mg/L (acetate: 3,959 mg/L, propionate: 66 mg/L, and butyrate: 116 mg/L) on day 39 and
333 dropped rapidly thereafter. Unfortunately, the subsequent profile of the SBY curve showed certain

334 irregularities caused by clogging of hoses for the feeding pumps by coagulated yeast biomass. The
335 biomass coagulated on days 47, 58, and 77. pH and the ammonium-nitrogen concentration increased
336 after urea addition from initial values of 6.62 and 809 mg/L on day 32 to 7.43 and 1,053 mg/L on day
337 64, respectively (Figure 4A). In order to prevent ammonia inhibition that threat by a pH increase [23],
338 urea addition was decreased by one third. This led to a decrease in the ammonium-nitrogen
339 concentration to 1,020 mg/L, but also to an increase in the acetate concentration from 527 mg/L on
340 day 64 to 1,662 mg/L on day 67. The return of urea addition to 48 mg/(L*d) did not show the desired
341 effect and the volatile acids concentrations rose again until the end of fermentation (Figure 4A). The
342 end concentrations were 3,228 mg/L, 335 mg/L, and 248 mg/L in the case of acetate, propionate, and
343 butyrate, respectively. Nevertheless, the pH remained almost stable despite the high VFA
344 concentrations (Figure 4B). The methane concentration remained almost stable during the entire
345 fermentation period at $66.3 \pm 4.2\%$.

346 The TS content was $2.26 \pm 0.26\%$ of fresh mass and the VS content was $62.8 \pm 2.34\%$ TS during the
347 fermentation.

348 Foaming occurred on days 4 and 16 overnight, when the foam reached as far as the lid of the
349 fermenter. No countermeasures were necessary since the foam had disappeared by the morning check
350 and there were only foam traces recognizable on the sides of the fermenter.

351

352 **4 Discussion**

353 Biogas yield using pure CYB in a continuous experiment showed lower values than the fermentation
354 batch tests until urea addition ($0.73 \text{ m}^3_{\text{N}}/\text{kg}_{\text{VS}}$ in continuous fermentation versus $0.86 \text{ m}^3_{\text{N}}/\text{kg}_{\text{VS}}$ in batch
355 tests). The nitrogen supplementation led to better usage of the CYB as a substrate. The biogas yield
356 increased by a factor of 2 and reached a maximum SBY of almost $1.45 \text{ m}^3_{\text{N}}/\text{kg}_{\text{VS}}$ during phases with
357 no disturbances. This is similar as in the case of the co-digestion of CYB and WFF (1:20) where the
358 maximum SBY reached $1.42 \text{ m}^3_{\text{N}}/\text{kg}_{\text{VS}}$ (not taking into account the SBY peak on day 4 that was
359 probably caused by the lag phase of the inoculum and thus sudden digestion of the WFF ratio of three
360 days at once). The SBY reached $1.32 \text{ m}^3_{\text{N}}/\text{kg}_{\text{VS}}$ in the preliminary experiment during the period of
361 continuous feeding at $2 \text{ kg}/(\text{m}^3 \cdot \text{d})$, which is in accordance with the mean SBY of $1.32 \text{ m}^3_{\text{N}}/\text{kg}_{\text{VS}}$

362 during the same OLR period in the continuous co-digestion experiment. These data appear to be high
363 compared to the batch experiments (e.g. SBY (WFF+CYB, 1:20) = $1.06 \pm 0.04 \text{ m}^3_{\text{N}}/\text{kg}_{\text{VS}}$). This is
364 probably due to the unequal degradation of the substrate, because the overall average SBY in the
365 continuous fermentation of the substrate mixture of CYB and WFF was $1.14 \pm 0.25 \text{ m}^3_{\text{N}}/\text{kg}_{\text{VS}}$.
366 Furthermore, it should be noted that the described experiments ran only a part of their hydraulic
367 retention time that is not the usual approach. These attempts can be understood as some kind of proof
368 of principle; further long-term experiments are to be done in order to confirm the findings presented
369 here.

370 As regards the literature data, there are only a few publications on yeast anaerobic digestion, and these
371 mainly deal with spent yeast from breweries in co-digestion with wastewater [13-16]. Zupančič et al.
372 [13] observed a biogas yield of $0.45\text{-}0.72 \text{ m}^3/\text{kg}_{\text{VS}}$ for brewery surplus yeast in batch fermentation
373 tests, which was lower than the SBY obtained in the batch experiment that is described in Table 2
374 ($0.86 \pm 0.04 \text{ m}^3_{\text{N}}/\text{kg}_{\text{VS}}$).

375 Even fewer publications can be found regarding the anaerobic digestion of waste frying fat. Labatut et
376 al. [24] described the anaerobic digestion of complex organic substrates, including vegetable oil. The
377 biogas yield curve showed similar behavior to the one in Figure 1. The authors explain that the initial
378 lag phase (of 12 days in their case) was caused by biochemical inhibition due to the accumulation of
379 long-chain fatty acids (LCFA) that are produced by the hydrolysis of neutral lipids. There are several
380 hypotheses regarding the inhibition mechanisms of LCFA in anaerobic digestion, e.g. sludge flotation
381 leading to washout, substrate, and product transport limitation from/to the cell due to the coating of the
382 cell by a layer of the LCFAs, and inhibition of methanogens (see [19] for an overview). The vegetable
383 oil used in the case of Labatut et al. [24] had a high methane potential of $0.68 \text{ m}^3_{\text{CH}_4}/\text{g}_{\text{VS}}$ when
384 compared with other measured substrates, and was somewhat lower than the SMY of WFF described
385 in Table 2 ($0.71 \pm 0.02 \text{ m}^3_{\text{CH}_4}/\text{g}_{\text{VS}}$).

386 The methane content in the continuous fermentation of pure CYB was similar to the fermentation
387 batch test (66.3% in continuous fermentation versus 67% in the batch test).

388 In the case of the co-digestion experiments of the CYB+WFF substrate mixture, the SBY in batch tests
389 was lower than in continuous experiments ($1.06 \text{ m}^3_{\text{N}}/\text{kg}_{\text{VS}}$ in the batch test versus $1.32 \text{ m}^3_{\text{N}}/\text{g}_{\text{VS}}$ in the

390 continuous experiment). This was probably caused by a worse distribution of the fat fraction in the
391 batch tests that were mixed once a day. In both cases, the methane concentration was as high as 67%.
392 The differences between the fermentation batch tests and continuous fermentation are in this case also
393 probably related to urea addition, which has a stabilizing effect on biogas production [25].
394 There are contradictory statements with regard to the design of feeding in the case of an anaerobic
395 digestion of fats in the literature [19]. According to Angelidaki & Ahring [26] the fats should be
396 introduced gradually and fed continuously to biogas reactors to allow for the maintenance of a
397 bacterial population capable of LCFA degradation and to prevent the accumulation of high
398 concentrations of LFCA that have a limiting effect. In contrast, Coelho et al. [27] tested various
399 operational conditions with a 6 h feeding time followed by a 6 h non-feeding time and a 3 h feeding
400 time followed by a 9 h non-feeding time, with variable feeding flows for each case. The authors stated
401 that an intermittent mode of feeding with longer feeding intermissions was more favorable for
402 anaerobic digestion of fat containing substrates as the non-feeding periods allow the biomass to
403 degrade the substrate adsorbed into the biomass during the feeding period. The results of the
404 preliminary experiment presented in Figure 2 show that the shortening of the intermissions from 24 h
405 to 1.5 h had a positive effect on biogas production from the substrate mixture of CYB+WFF.
406 Cavaleiro et al. [28] made an interesting observation in the case of the use of oleic acid as a substrate
407 that a start-up strategy combining feeding phases and batch degradation phases promoted the
408 development of microorganisms, which are capable of anaerobic digestion of LCFA. Indeed, the
409 acclimation of the microflora was necessary in the fermentation experiments with a high ratio of WFF
410 as a substrate, as can be seen in the lag phase of the batch tests (Figure 1). The biogas peaks on day 4
411 in the co-digestion experiments in CSTRs (Figures 2A and 3A) and the smaller biogas peak on day 6
412 in continuous fermentation of pure CYB (Figure 4A) imply that the substrate remained unused during
413 the first days and all remaining fat was digested at once after the start of fat digestion.
414 The mean pH value of the digestate during the mono-digestion of CYB was higher than that of
415 digestate from co-digestion of CYB+WFF (7.11 ± 0.27 versus 6.85 ± 0.12 , respectively). This is
416 surprising as the VFA concentration in CYB fermentation reached much higher values than in the case

417 of mixed substrate fermentation (the maximum VFA concentrations were 4,139 mg/L for CYB and 27
418 mg/L in the case of CYB+WFF).

419 The TOC/TN ratio in the case of the CYB+WFF fermentation was higher than in the case of sole CYB
420 fermentation (the maximum TOC/TN was 5.1 in the case of CYB alone and 4.1 in the case of
421 CYB+WFF fermentation). As described in Moeller et al. [29], the C/N ratio of digestate during the
422 fermentation of C-rich substrates has an effect on the formation of foam. The authors showed that the
423 application of certain nitrogen fertilizers can prevent foam formation in anaerobic digestion plants that
424 utilize sugar beet as a substrate. The decrease of the C/N ratio in the substrate mixture has apparently a
425 stabilizing effect on the biogas process with regard to foaming. Two foaming periods were observed
426 during the fermentation of CYB. The first foaming that occurred during the anaerobic digestion of
427 CYB+WFF can be regarded as typical for the start-up stage of anaerobic digestion, as has been
428 described by anaerobic digestion plant operators [30]. The second foaming event occurred during the
429 changeover of the OLR. However, the serious long-term foaming that is typical for substrates with
430 high C/N ratios did not occur. It is possible that the digestate did not foam steadily because urea use
431 caused the required stabilization of the digestate. Despite the absence of foaming, the mono-digestion
432 of CYB was not stable enough to further increase the OLR.

433 In summary, the anaerobic digestion process with the CYB was not easy to perform due to its
434 tendency for over-acidification to occur and due to the coagulation of the CYB in the feeding device.
435 In contrast, the co-digestion of CYB with WFF ran in a stable manner up to an OLR of 2 kg/(m³*d).
436 Zupančič et al. [13] advise against the use of yeast as a mono-substrate in anaerobic digestion due to
437 the ammonia inhibition that is caused by the high TN contents of 11-13 g/L. However, in the case of
438 CYB fermentation the situation seems to be opposite, as the TN concentration in the yeast was only
439 1.92 g/L meaning that not only C/N ratios that are too low as in the case of Zupančič et al. [13] but
440 also high C/N of 70.1 can cause problems during mono-fermentation. Neira & Jeison [15] investigated
441 the co-digestion of surplus yeast and wastewater from a brewery. They described the anaerobic
442 digestion process as feasible with no negative effects during 70 days of UASB reactor operation.
443 Zupančič et al. [14] also observed no adverse effects up to 1.1% (v/v) of yeast and wastewater.

444 However, at concentrations over 2.8% (v/v) process failures were detected, such as biomass washout
445 with the consequent diminished operating capacity.

446 Further research is needed in order to test the long-time stability of the co-digestion of CYB-WFF
447 substrate mixtures. In addition, the stabilization of the yeast biomass with regard to coagulation is
448 necessary in order to make the process more feasible for use in practice.

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484 **Conflict of interest statement**

485 *The authors have declared no conflict of interest.*

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584 **Tables**585 **Table 1** Parameters and analytical methods for the evaluation of CYB and digestate samples

Parameter	Sample pre-treatment	Analytical methods
TS	none	DIN 12880
VS	none	DIN 12879
Protein concentration	filtered	Bradford reaction with Coomassie [®] Brilliant Blue R-250 (AppliChem GmbH, Germany) , photometric measurement with UV-1601 (Shimadzu, Japan) at 595 nm
Fat concentration	drying, milling	Determination by use of Soxhlet extraction apparatus (Soxtherm [®] /Multistat, C. Gerhardt GmbH & Co. KG, Germany) by use of petroleum ether 30/40 as a solvent
NH ₄ -N concentration	filtered	DIN 38406 E5, Spektroquant [®] test kit (measuring range 0.01-3 mg L ⁻¹ NH ₄ -N, Merck, Germany), photometric measurement with MultiLab P5 (WTW, Weilheim, Germany)
Acetate, propionate, butyrate concentrations	filtered	High performance liquid chromatography (Shimadzu, Japan); detector: RID-10A; column: VA 300/7.8 Nucleogel Ion 300 OA; eluent: 0.01 N H ₂ SO ₄

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596 **Table 2** Results of the fermentation batch tests

597 CYB = concentrated yeast biomass, SBY = specific biogas yield, SMY = specific methane yield, WFF

598 = waste frying fat

Substrate	SBY [m ³ _N /kg _{VS}]	SMY [m ³ _N /kg _{VS}]	Methane [%]
CYB	0.862 ± 0.04	0.573 ± 0.04	67 ± 1
WFF	1.08 ± 0.05	0.705 ± 0.02	67 ± 3
CYB + WFF (1:20)	1.06 ± 0.04	0.750 ± 0.00	71 ± 2
CYB + WFF (1:1)	0.85 ± 0.00	0.587 ± 0.01	69 ± 1

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616 **Figure legends**

617 Figure 1: Specific biogas yields using substrates and substrate mixtures at two different ratios

618 Figure 2: (A) Specific biogas yield, expected specific biogas yield according to the batch test results
619 (Table 2), and volatile fatty acids concentrations (acetate, propionate and butyrate) as well as (B)
620 hourly produced biogas during the preliminary experiment using the CYB-WFF substrate mixture
621 (1:20).

622 Figure 3: (A) Specific biogas yield, expected specific biogas yield according to the batch test results
623 (Table 2), and acetate concentration, and (B) nitrogen addition, pH value, TOC/TN ratio and NH₄-N
624 concentration in the course of the co-digestion of CYB and WFF at a ratio of 1:20.

625 Figure 4: (A) Specific biogas yield, expected specific biogas yield according to the batch test results
626 (Table 2), and volatile fatty acids (acetate, propionate and butyrate) concentrations, and (B) nitrogen
627 addition, pH value, TOC/TN ratio and NH₄-N concentration during the mono-digestion of the
628 concentrated yeast biomass.

629 (N added is the amount of the nitrogen added to the fermenter along with the substrate mixture per day
630 related to the fermenter volume)

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 678 addition, pH value, TOC/TN ratio and $\text{NH}_4\text{-N}$ concentration during the mono-digestion of the
 679 concentrated yeast biomass.
 680 (N added is the amount of the nitrogen added to the fermenter along with the substrate mixture per day
 681 related to the fermenter volume)

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